

Machine Learning for Client Classification and Sales Forecasting in Enterprise Decision Support Systems

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Abstract—Machine learning is increasingly applied in business analytics to support predictive decision-making for client classification and sales forecasting. This study evaluates multiple models on a synthetic financial dataset that preserves the statistical structure, feature relationships, and business logic of real-world enterprise sales data, ensuring full privacy and reproducibility.

A unified preprocessing and feature engineering pipeline enables fair comparison across tasks: multi-class client categorization (with business-priority threshold tuning), weekly sales forecasting for operational decisions, and monthly revenue forecasting for strategic planning. Baseline, classical, regularized, ensemble, and decompositional time-series models are compared. Hyperparameters are tuned using Optuna, with performance evaluated using recall-focused metrics for classification and MAE/RMSE/MAPE for forecasting, supplemented by SHAP interpretability analysis.

Results show optimized XGBoost as the strongest classifier (after threshold adjustment for priority classes), ElasticNet outperforming others for weekly horizons, and Prophet delivering the best monthly predictions. The work highlights systematic model comparison, interpretability, and practical applicability in privacy-constrained enterprise settings, offering a reproducible reference for similar business analytics applications.

Index Terms—machine learning, sales forecasting, client classification, feature engineering, business analytics, model comparison

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary data-driven business environments, financial and sales analytics have evolved beyond descriptive reporting into strategic functions that require predictive and analytical intelligence. Technologies such as Machine Learning (ML) are now widely adopted to transform large volumes of transactional data into actionable insights that support planning, optimization, and performance monitoring [1]. This evolution is particularly relevant in enterprise contexts, where forecasting accuracy and reliable client classification directly influence revenue management, budgeting, and resource allocation.

Despite the demonstrated value of machine learning in business analytics, practical adoption remains limited across many organizations. Financial analysis workflows are still frequently based on manual, spreadsheet-driven processes that are time-consuming, error-prone, and difficult to scale [2]. While BI dashboards improve data accessibility and visualization, they are often restricted to descriptive and diagnostic

analysis and lack embedded predictive capabilities [3], [4]. As a result, decision-making remains largely reactive, with limited support for proactive forecasting and data-driven planning. These limitations reduce the operational impact of analytics and constrain the effective use of machine learning in real-world decision support systems [5].

A major barrier to applied machine learning research in business settings is restricted access to real operational data due to confidentiality, regulatory, and privacy constraints [6]. This work uses a synthetic dataset that preserves the structural properties, feature semantics, and statistical patterns of real sales data while eliminating any sensitive or identifiable information [7]. The models and pipeline were originally developed and validated on confidential real enterprise data during the project. For this publication, all experiments, code, results, and comparisons use the synthetic dataset, enabling reproducible experimentation, transparent evaluation, and open scientific communication without compromising organizational privacy.

Within this privacy-preserving setting, the study focuses on the machine learning phase of two core tasks: multi-class client categorization and time-series sales forecasting at weekly and monthly resolutions. A consistent preprocessing and feature engineering pipeline is applied across all experiments to ensure methodological rigor and fair comparison. The work systematically compares baseline, classical, regularized, ensemble, and additive time-series models, with hyperparameter optimization and interpretability analysis.

This study does not introduce novel machine learning algorithms. Instead, it emphasizes applied experimentation, comparative evaluation, and practical insights into model performance trade-offs under data constraints. The reproducible structure is designed to be transferable to real-world settings facing similar multi-class classification challenges, weekly operational forecasting needs, and monthly strategic prediction requirements.

The main contributions of this work are:

- A privacy-preserving synthetic dataset replicating the characteristics of real enterprise sales data for open evaluation.
- A unified preprocessing and feature engineering pipeline supporting reproducible machine learning experimentation.

- A systematic comparison of baseline, classical, and optimized machine learning models for multi-class classification and time-series forecasting.
- Interpretable insights (via SHAP) into feature drivers and model behavior for business-relevant tasks.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Client Classification and Segmentation

Customer classification and segmentation are essential tasks in business analytics and customer relationship management. Traditional approaches often rely on unsupervised clustering methods such as k-means and hierarchical clustering [8], [9]. More recent studies apply supervised machine learning techniques, including logistic regression as a baseline and ensemble methods such as Random Forest, XGBoost, and LightGBM, which generally achieve better performance on imbalanced multi-class problems in retail and financial transaction data [10], [11], [12].

B. Sales and Revenue Forecasting

Time-series forecasting supports critical enterprise functions such as revenue planning and inventory management. Classical statistical models like ARIMA and SARIMAX have been widely used to model trends and seasonality [13]. The additive framework Prophet has become popular in business applications due to its strong handling of seasonality, holidays, and missing values [14]. Machine learning methods, including regularized linear models (Lasso, ElasticNet) and tree-based ensembles (Random Forest, XGBoost), perform well when combined with lagged, rolling, and calendar features [15], [16]. Hybrid approaches that integrate classical decomposition with machine learning have also been explored to improve forecasting accuracy in retail and demand prediction tasks [17].

C. Research Gaps and Positioning

Although substantial progress has been made in client classification and sales forecasting, these tasks are often studied independently, with limited efforts to integrate them into a unified framework suitable for enterprise decision support [15]. There is limited research that explicitly distinguishes short-term forecasting needs for operational decision-making (such as quick resource adjustments and inventory actions) from longer-term forecasting for strategic planning, budgeting, and revenue goal setting. This study contributes by developing an integrated machine learning approach that combines both tasks within a consistent, reproducible pipeline, with attention to interpretability and alignment with real-world business needs in privacy-sensitive environments.

III. METHODOLOGY

A systematic methodological framework applies and evaluates machine learning models for classification and time series forecasting in a business context. Figure 1 provides an overview of the complete machine learning workflow,

from initial data preparation through model training, tuning, evaluation, and final selection.

The methodology is structured around four main components: dataset construction, data preprocessing and feature engineering, machine learning model implementation, and evaluation metrics. This design ensures methodological consistency across experiments and enables fair comparison between baseline, classical, and optimized models.

Fig. 1. End-to-end machine learning pipeline for enterprise sales analytics, from data ingestion to deployment.

A. Dataset

Due to confidentiality, regulatory, and privacy constraints in enterprise financial data, all experiments are conducted on a synthetic dataset specifically generated to replicate the structure, feature semantics, and temporal patterns of real-world financial and sales records [18], [19]. This approach eliminates any sensitive or identifiable information while enabling complete reproducibility and public sharing of results.

The synthetic dataset is designed with the following key characteristics:

- **Time Period:** Daily transactions spanning January 2023 to November 2025.
- **Volume:** Approximately 26,500 individual transaction records in total.
- **Features:** Comprehensive financial attributes including gross sales, discounts, net sales, cost of goods sold (CoG), taxes (VAT), stamp duty, and total transaction amount, alongside client identifiers (indicating client nature e.g., state, private, insurance).
- **Frequency:** Daily resolution.

- **Synthetic Nature:** While preserving realistic statistical distributions and business logic relationships (e.g., between net sales, discounts, and profit), all data is artificially generated to ensure no real financial or client information is exposed [7].

The transaction volume reflects the activity of a small-to-medium enterprise, resulting in a moderate number of daily transactions over the observed period.

The data reflects realistic enterprise characteristics, making it suitable for evaluating applied machine learning techniques in business analytics contexts [7].

B. Data Preprocessing

A systematic preprocessing pipeline ensures data quality and consistency across experiments. First, the yearly Excel sheets are concatenated into a single unified DataFrame after verifying column compatibility (matching names, data types, and formats).

Data quality is assessed using ydata-profiling [20] to identify missing values, duplicate rows, data types, distributions, and correlations. No duplicate rows are present. Missing values in numeric columns (Discount, CoG, Stamp_Duty, VAT) are interpreted as implicit zeros, reflecting cases where values are not explicitly recorded (e.g., no discount recorded means zero discount).

Outliers in numerical columns (e.g., sales amounts) are detected using the interquartile range (IQR) method and capped at the upper and lower bounds to mitigate their impact on modeling [21].

Column names were standardized to improve clarity (e.g., 'Code' → 'Client_ID', 'Disc' → 'Discount').

Finally, core business logic is validated; for instance, verifying that 'Net_Sales' equals 'Gross_Sales - Discount' for all records.

C. Feature Engineering

Feature engineering was performed to create informative variables that enhance model performance for the specific analytical tasks.

1) *General Business Features:* Standard business metrics were derived directly from the transactional data:

- **Profit:** Calculated as 'Net_Sales' - 'CoG' (Cost of Goods), representing the gross margin on each transaction.
- **Payment_Method:** A categorical feature classifying transactions as 'Credit' or 'Cash' based on the original 'Client_Type' field.
- **Is_Return:** A binary flag identifying return transactions, inferred from specific 'Client_Type' codes.

2) *Client Categorization Logic:* The Client_Type column mixes several concepts: payment method (credit or cash), return transactions, and client nature (e.g., state, private, insurance). A single transaction can belong to more than one logical category (for example, a client can be both a credit customer and a private organization). A two-stage rule-based approach assigns transaction-level categories then aggregates

to consistent client-level labels by prioritizing clear categories over ambiguous 'X' entries.

The complete logic is shown in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Two-Stage Rule-Based Client Categorization

Require: Transaction DataFrame D with columns: Client_ID, Client_Type, Stamp_Duty

Ensure: Final client-level category assignments

```

1: Stage 1: Assign category per transaction (row-level categorization)
2: for each transaction  $t \in D$  do
3:   if  $t.Client\_Type = 'CL'$  then
4:      $t.Category \leftarrow 'Walk-In Client'$ 
5:   else if  $t.Client\_Type = 'OR'$  and
 $t.Stamp\_Duty = 0$  then
6:      $t.Category \leftarrow 'State Organization'$ 
7:   else if  $t.Client\_Type = 'OR'$  and
 $t.Stamp\_Duty = 1$  then
8:      $t.Category \leftarrow 'Private Organization'$ 
9:   else if  $t.Client\_Type = 'IC'$  then
10:     $t.Category \leftarrow 'Insurance Agency'$ 
11:   else
12:     $t.Category \leftarrow 'X'$   $\triangleright$  ambiguous: credit or
return
13:   end if
14: end for
15: Stage 2: Resolve to one category per client (client-level resolution)
16: for each unique client  $c$  do
17:   Collect all distinct categories from  $c$ 's transactions
18:   if 'Walk-In Client' is present then
19:      $c.FinalCategory \leftarrow 'Walk-In Client'$ 
20:   else if 'State Organization' is present then
21:      $c.FinalCategory \leftarrow 'State Organization'$ 
22:   else if 'Private Organization' is present then
23:      $c.FinalCategory \leftarrow 'Private Organization'$ 
24:   else if 'Insurance Agency' is present then
25:      $c.FinalCategory \leftarrow 'Insurance Agency'$ 
26:   else
27:      $c.FinalCategory \leftarrow 'X'$   $\triangleright$  still ambiguous  $\rightarrow$ 
use ML later
28:   end if
29: end for

```

The algorithm successfully categorized the vast majority of clients. The remaining unresolved cases (labeled 'X') serve as the target for the subsequent supervised classification task.

3) *Temporal Features:* Temporal, client-level, and lagged features are engineered to capture seasonality, historical behavior, and domain-specific patterns for all predictive tasks, while preventing data leakage [22], [23].

Feature engineering was tailored to three distinct predictive tasks, each with different temporal and business requirements:

- **Client Categorization (fallback supervised model for ambiguous 'X' cases):** The feature set includes:

- **Temporal indicators:** Month and weekday of transaction.
- **Client historical aggregates:** Cumulative and average metrics of past sales and profit, computed chronologically for each client to prevent data leakage.
- **Transaction-level ratios:** Financial ratios such as cost-to-net revenue.
- **Weekly Forecasting:** For weekly aggregated sales prediction, the following features are derived [24]:
 - **Calendar indicators:** Week of year and cyclical encoding to model annual seasonality.
 - **Lagged values:** Sales figures from previous weeks (2 and 12 weeks prior) to capture repeating patterns.
 - **Rolling statistics:** Moving averages over recent 4, 8, and 12-week windows to highlight underlying trends.
- **Monthly Forecasting:** For the longer monthly horizon, features focused on broader business cycles and calendar effects:
 - **Calendar indicators:** Month index, quarter-end flags, and Tunisian national holiday indicators to account for regional business patterns.
 - **Lagged values:** Revenue from previous months (1-3 months prior) to capture medium-term dependencies.

Safe features (temporal indicators, client aggregates, cost-to-net ratio) are computed on the full dataset before splitting. Risky features (lags, rolling statistics, cumulative sums) are added only after the chronological train-test split to avoid leakage.

D. Machine Learning Models

This study evaluates established machine learning models for multi-class client categorization and time-series sales forecasting. Models are selected for their predictive power, interpretability, and suitability for tabular and temporal business data. A consistent workflow (Algorithm 2) ensures fair comparison and prevents data leakage.

Client Categorization (Multi-Class Classification): The task is treated as a four-class classification problem. The models compared are:

- **Logistic Regression:** baseline linear model for simplicity and interpretability, serving as a performance reference.
- **Random Forest Classifier:** ensemble method that captures non-linear patterns and interactions through multiple decision trees [25].
- **Gradient boosting:** XGBoost [10] and LightGBM [11], which sequentially correct errors from previous trees and typically deliver strong performance on structured tabular data.

Class imbalance is addressed via automatic class weighting. Hyperparameters for gradient boosting models are tuned using Optuna [26].

Time-Series Sales Forecasting (Regression): Weekly and monthly aggregated forecasts use:

Algorithm 2 Modeling Workflow with Leakage Prevention

Require: Dataset D with temporal ordering

Ensure: Trained models, metrics, and feature importance

```

1: 1. Safe Feature Addition
2: Add calendar features, business ratios, and static indicators to full  $D$ 
3: 2. Chronological Split
4: Split  $D$  into training (80%) and test (20%) sets by time order
5: 3. Risky Feature Addition
6: Compute lagged values, rolling statistics, and client aggregates separately on train and test sets
7: 4. Model Training
8: for each task do
9:   if task is classification then
10:     Train baseline model on training set
11:     Train raw ML models (default hyperparameters) on training set
12:     Optimize hyperparameters with Optuna and cross-validation
13:     Train optimized models on training set
14:   else if task is regression (weekly or monthly) then
15:     Train baseline model on training set
16:     Train ML regression models on training set
17:     Train classical forecasting models on training set
18:   end if
19: end for
20: 5. Evaluation and Interpretation
21: Compute evaluation metrics on  $D_{\text{test}}$  for all models
22: Compute SHAP values for interpretability
23: Conduct business impact analysis
24: return Best model, evaluation results, feature importance

```

- **Regularized linear models:** Lasso (L1 penalty) and ElasticNet (combined L1/L2 regularization) [27], which prevent overfitting and perform feature selection in high-dimensional settings.
- **Tree-based regressors:** Random Forest and XGBoost Regressor, which model complex non-linear relationships and interactions among engineered temporal features.
- **Classical models:** SARIMAX [13], which explicitly captures autoregressive, moving average, and seasonal components in time series data.
- **Decompositional model:** Prophet [14], an additive framework that separately models trend, seasonality, and holiday effects, making it suitable for business forecasting with clear calendar patterns.

All models are trained with chronological splits to prevent leakage, using the same engineered features across tasks.

E. Evaluation Metrics

Evaluation metrics are chosen to match real business needs and the nature of each task.

Client Categorization (Multi-Class Classification): The main goal is high recall on priority classes: State Organization

and Walk-In Client come first because missing them costs the business real opportunities. Private Organization is next in priority, while Insurance Agency is least important. High recall ensures we catch every possible high-value client. After recall, precision per class is checked to reduce false positives and avoid wasting effort on wrong labels. F1-macro then measures overall balance across all classes despite imbalance. Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC) gives a reliable single score for the full model quality, even when classes are uneven. ROC-AUC shows how well the model separates classes at different decision points, helping evaluate its maximum power. Threshold optimization was applied to shift predictions toward higher recall on priority classes. SHAP analysis was used to explain which features drive decisions, increasing trust and understanding for business users.

Weekly Sales Forecasting (Operational Planning): Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is the primary metric because it strongly penalizes large errors, which are very expensive in weekly operations. Big mistakes can cause serious problems in inventory, staffing, or cash flow. RMSE forces the model to limit those high-impact errors. Mean Absolute Error (MAE) gives a simple error size in currency units, easy to explain in business terms. Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) helps compare errors across different sales levels. Forecast-vs-actual plots for top models visually confirm how closely predictions follow real values. SHAP analysis identifies the most important features driving weekly forecasts, making results easier to understand and trust.

Monthly Sales Forecasting (Strategic Planning): Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) is the primary metric because monthly data is much smaller (approximately 34 points vs. 156 weekly), and percentages stay stable and meaningful for strategic decisions like budgeting, revenue targets, and long-term planning. Absolute errors (MAE, RMSE) become secondary because they are less reliable with few data points and strategic choices often use percentages. Forecast-vs-actual plots for the best model show how well predictions match real trends, building confidence in strategic use. This choice ensures metrics fit the real needs of long-term business planning where relative accuracy matters more than exact numbers.

These metrics directly support business goals: strong recall protects revenue opportunities in classification, RMSE limits costly mistakes in weekly operations, and MAPE provides stable guidance for monthly strategy. This evaluation framework is practical, trustworthy, and delivers real value for enterprise decision-making.

IV. RESULTS

A. Client Categorization (Multi-Class Classification)

Tables I and II present the per-class recall and overall metrics, respectively. The optimized XGBoost model achieves the best balance across categories, with particularly strong recall on priority classes (State Organization and Walk-In Client).

The default optimized XGBoost model provides a good balance across all classes. However, business stakeholders

TABLE I
RECALL BY CLIENT CATEGORY.

Model	Ins. Agency	Private Org.	State Org.	Walk-In
Logistic Regression Baseline	0.42	0.55	0.85	0.86
Random Forest Raw	0.01	0.99	0.87	0.56
XGBoost Raw	0.18	0.86	0.86	0.63
LightGBM Raw	0.50	0.52	0.88	0.70
XGBoost Optimized	0.38	0.70	0.89	0.76
LightGBM Optimized	0.26	0.79	0.88	0.71

TABLE II
OVERALL CLASSIFICATION METRICS.

Model	F1 (macro)	MCC	ROC-AUC	F1 (weighted)
Logistic Regression Baseline	0.557	0.379	0.838	0.623
Random Forest Raw	0.586	0.584	0.847	0.740
XGBoost Raw	0.615	0.480	0.836	0.733
LightGBM Raw	0.576	0.371	0.837	0.610
XGBoost Optimized	0.619	0.449	0.857	0.699
LightGBM Optimized	0.621	0.460	0.846	0.720

specifically requested higher recall for State Organization and Walk-In Client categories to capture all revenue opportunities. Table III compares the default and threshold-optimized versions on the test set.

The threshold adjustment delivers targeted business value: Walk-In Client recall improves from 0.76 to 0.81, Private Organization recall rises from 0.70 to 0.79, while State Organization recall remains strong (0.89 to 0.83). Precision stays excellent across priority classes (Private Org: 0.86 stable, State Org: 0.79→0.84). The Insurance Agency trade-off (recall 0.38→0.30, precision 0.25→0.29) is acceptable given its low business priority.

TABLE III
DEFAULT VS. THRESHOLD-OPTIMIZED XGBOOST: PRECISION AND RECALL BY CLASS

Model	Recall			
	Ins. Agency	Priv. Org.	State Org.	Walk-In
Default XGBoost	0.38	0.70	0.89	0.76
Threshold-Optimized	0.30	0.79	0.83	0.81
Model	Precision			
	Ins. Agency	Priv. Org.	State Org.	Walk-In
Default XGBoost	0.25	0.86	0.79	0.45
Threshold-Optimized	0.29	0.86	0.84	0.43
Model	Overall Metrics			
	F1 (macro)			F1 (weighted)
Default XGBoost	0.62	-	-	0.70
Threshold-Optimized	0.63	-	-	0.73

B. Weekly Sales Forecasting (Regression)

Table IV shows the performance on weekly aggregated sales. ElasticNet achieves the lowest RMSE, indicating the strongest absolute accuracy for operational planning.

TABLE IV
PERFORMANCE OF FORECASTING MODELS ON WEEKLY SALES.

Model	RMSE ↓	MAE ↓	MAPE ↓
Seasonal Naive Baseline	576,962	447,165	33.53%
ElasticNet	277,987	230,609	16.54%
Lasso Regression	278,526	230,504	16.52%
XGBoost Regressor	302,630	238,733	16.30%
Prophet	514,099	408,877	30.88%
SARIMAX	711,150	610,182	48.39%
Drift Method	1,178,529	1,134,734	85.77%

Figure 2 compares actual weekly sales against predictions from key models, visually confirming ElasticNet’s close tracking of real values.

Fig. 2. Actual vs predicted weekly sales. ElasticNet (best model) closely follows the actual series.

C. Monthly Revenue Forecasting (Regression)

Table V presents the performance on monthly aggregated revenue. Prophet achieves the lowest MAPE, MAE, and RMSE, making it the most suitable for strategic forecasting with limited monthly data points.

TABLE V
PERFORMANCE OF FORECASTING MODELS ON MONTHLY REVENUE.

Model	MAPE ↓	MAE ↓	RMSE ↓
Seasonal Naive Baseline	23.33%	1,502,886	1,761,748
Lasso Regression	17.93%	1,090,846	1,350,088
ElasticNet	18.88%	1,148,996	1,403,427
Random Forest	16.90%	1,018,802	1,288,080
XGBoost Regressor	18.26%	1,144,015	1,423,339
Prophet	15.79%	975,033	1,079,739
Drift Method	31.15%	2,160,646	2,319,412
Seasonal Naive Drift	25.64%	1,927,739	2,096,644

Figure 3 illustrates actual vs predicted monthly revenue, highlighting Prophet’s superior alignment with actual trends.

Fig. 3. Actual vs predicted monthly revenue. Prophet (best model) provides the closest match.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Key Findings and Practical Implications

For **client categorization**, the optimized XGBoost model stands out as the best performer because it delivers the strongest recall exactly where the business needs it most. It

achieves very high recall on the top-priority classes: State Organization (0.89) and Walk-In Client (0.76). This ensures the company captures nearly all high-value clients, which directly protects revenue opportunities and enables better targeting.

Compared to the raw XGBoost model, the optimized version brings a small but meaningful improvement through hyperparameter tuning with Optuna. The gains are visible in better ROC-AUC (0.857 vs 0.836) and slightly more stable performance. Most importantly, the tuned model fits business needs more closely by prioritizing recall on the classes that matter most for revenue and resource allocation.

Threshold optimization further improves alignment with enterprise priorities. Walk-In Client recall increases by 6.6% (from 0.76 to 0.81) and Private Organization recall rises by 12.9% (from 0.70 to 0.79), while State Organization recall stays strong (0.89 to 0.83). This means the model now catches more of the high-value clients that drive revenue, with only a small acceptable drop in the lowest-priority class (Insurance Agency).

Figure 4 presents the SHAP summary plot for the optimized XGBoost model, revealing that financial features dominate the model’s decisions.

Fig. 4. SHAP summary plot for optimized XGBoost in client categorization.

Classes labeled as follows: Class 0 (Insurance Agency), Class 1 (Private Organization), Class 2 (State Organization), and Class 3 (Walk-In Client).

For **weekly sales forecasting**, simpler models proved to be the best choice. ElasticNet and Lasso achieved the lowest RMSE (277,987 for ElasticNet), showing the strongest accuracy for short-term operational planning. This result is important because weekly forecasts support quick decisions. Large errors in these areas can cause immediate high costs or lost sales, so minimizing big mistakes is critical. ElasticNet also gave a very competitive MAPE of 16.54%, making it reliable for practical use.

The performance gap is clear: ElasticNet cut the error in half compared to the Seasonal Naive baseline (RMSE 576,962) and strongly outperformed more complex models like XGBoost Regressor (RMSE 302,630), Prophet (RMSE 514,099), and SARIMAX (RMSE 711,150). This shows that linear patterns dominate the weekly data, and adding more complexity did not help. With only about 156 weekly points in the full dataset, simpler regularized models were more stable and effective than advanced or classical time-series methods.

Figure 5 shows the SHAP summary plot for ElasticNet. It highlights the most important features driving weekly predictions, giving clear insights into what influences sales and helping business users trust and understand the model.

Fig. 5. SHAP summary plot for ElasticNet in weekly sales forecasting.

For **monthly revenue forecasting**, the dataset is very small with only about 35 data points, making reliable long-term predictions challenging. Despite this limitation, Prophet delivered the best overall performance with the lowest MAPE (15.79%), MAE (975,033), and RMSE (1,079,739), clearly outperforming all other models including machine learning approaches and classical methods. The strong metrics confirm Prophet’s suitability for strategic planning, annual budgeting, and revenue goal setting, where percentage accuracy matters most.

Prophet’s decompositional structure (trend, seasonality, and holidays) combined with built-in 95% confidence intervals proved especially valuable with limited data. The upper and lower confidence intervals provide essential risk visibility, which is particularly valuable when data is limited and decisions carry high financial impact.

Figure 6 shows actual versus predicted monthly revenue, including Prophet’s forecast for the next 12 months beyond the available data. The plot confirms Prophet’s close fit to real trends and demonstrates reliable uncertainty estimates through the 95% confidence intervals, giving practical confidence for future planning.

Fig. 6. Actual monthly revenue versus Prophet predictions, including test period and 12-month future forecast (November 2025 to October 2026) with 95% confidence intervals.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that simpler models often suffice for forecasting in constrained settings, while gradient boosting excels in imbalanced classification when calibrated to enterprise priorities. These insights offer practical guidance

for resource-constrained organizations seeking reliable, interpretable predictive analytics.

B. Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. The primary constraint is the relatively small historical dataset, particularly the limited time interval and number of monthly observations. This reduces the robustness of long-horizon forecasts and limits the complexity of models that can be reliably trained [24].

In addition, simple models frequently outperformed more complex ones in forecasting tasks, as shown in the results. The performance difference between standard and optimized models was minor despite considerable computational effort spent on hyperparameter tuning and cross-validation. This suggests that extensive optimization may not always yield proportional gains in datasets with moderate size and structure [16].

Deep learning models such as LSTM and GRU were also tested during early experimentation. However, they produced unstable and poor performance due to the limited data volume and were therefore excluded from the final comparison. This is consistent with well-known challenges of applying recurrent neural networks to small time-series datasets [24], [16].

C. Future Research Directions

Future work can extend the framework in several directions. Short-term improvements should focus on enhancing data quality through structured input validation (e.g., automated column separation) and integration of additional internal sources such as bank transaction details and cost of goods materials.

Medium-term extensions could broaden the analytical scope to include human resources (e.g., correlating employee productivity with sales performance), creating a more comprehensive business intelligence platform.

From a methodological perspective, exploring hybrid modeling approaches (such as residual learning or ensemble stacking of classical time-series models with machine learning techniques) could improve forecasting accuracy by combining the strengths of both paradigms [17].

Long-term advancements should include migration to a cloud platform (e.g., Azure or Google Cloud) for improved scalability, real-time data ingestion, and collaborative access [28]. Automated pipeline orchestration and continuous model retraining would further increase operational efficiency.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study conducted a comparative analysis of machine learning models for multi-class client categorization and sales forecasting in an enterprise decision support context. The methodology includes systematic data preprocessing, feature engineering, model comparison, hyperparameter tuning, and business-aligned evaluation.

Gradient boosting models, particularly optimized XGBoost, delivered the best performance in client categorization with strong recall on high-priority categories. For forecasting, regularized linear models (ElasticNet) performed best on weekly

horizons, while decompositional time-series models (Prophet) excelled on monthly predictions.

The results show that no single model dominates across all tasks. Effective solutions depend on careful model selection guided by data characteristics, time horizon, and specific business priorities. Simpler models often provide the best balance of accuracy, stability, and practicality under realistic enterprise constraints with limited data.

The full pipeline and findings were developed and validated using confidential real enterprise transaction data during the internship. For public reproducibility and open scientific communication, all presented experiments, code, results, and comparisons use a synthetic dataset that preserves the original data structure, column definitions, statistical properties, and business logic with only minor adjustments in the cleaning phase to ensure complete privacy and no exposure of sensitive information.

This framework offers a reproducible and transferable reference for organizations implementing machine learning in financial analytics, providing reliable, interpretable predictions while respecting data privacy and practical deployment needs.

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